

BHU**Management
Review**

A JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY MANAGEMENT RESEARCH

Vol. 3, Issue-1, Jan.-June 2012

FMS

Banaras Hindu University

Improving Organizational Performance Through
Supply Chain Management Practices by Indian Paint Industry
**Prof. Deepak Barman, Dr. Ashutosh Mohan
Gyaneshwar Singh Kushwaha**

System Modeling and Business Performance Evaluation
D.K. Banwet, K.K. Goswami, Propa Goswami

Impact of Stress on the Job Satisfaction and Organizational
Commitment of the Sales Force of Pharmaceutical Industry: A Case Study
Prof. S. K. Singh, Vivek Tiwari, Rajeev Kumar Malik

Consequences of the Organised Retail
and the FDIs over Retail Sector in India
Dr. G. C. Jaiswal, Dharen Kumar Pandey

Factors Affecting Corporate Dividend Policy:
A Case of Nepalese Corporations
Prof. Raj Kumar, Pawan Kumar Jha

Role of Television Advertising in Attitude Formation
and Purchase Intention- A Study in Indian Telecom Sector
Dr. Sathya Swaroop Debasish, Mr. A Mohan Muralidhar

Sustainable Development Through Marketing:
A Reflection from Retail Industry
Dr. Ranjana Pandey, Prof. Usha Kiran Rai

Intangible Value of Corporate India
(Intangible Share in Total Value of Indian Companies)
Dr. Shital Jhunjunwala

Impact of Celebrity Endorsement on Consumers'
Buying Decisions
Dr. S. K. Dubey, Mr. Pradeep Agarwal

Competitive Advantage through Human Resources:
A Study in Punjab National Bank
Saloni Pahuja

Environmental Accountability: An Urge of Environment to
Bring Some Genuine Changes in Corporate Practices
and People's Lifestyle
Dr. R.K. Lodhwal, Ms. Kanchan Lata Tripathi

BHU MANAGEMENT REVIEW
A Journal of Contemporary Management Research

Chief Patron
Dean
Faculty of Management Studies
Banaras Hindu University

Patron
Prof. H. C. Chaudhary
Prof. D. Barman
Prof. P. S. Tripathi

Editor-in-Chief
Prof. S. K. Singh

Managing Editor
Prof. Raj Kumar

Associate Editor
Dr. Ashutosh Mohan
Dr. Abhijeet Singh

International Advisory Board
Prof. S. P. Singh, Canada
Dr. Claudia Chiru, Romania
Dr. Paul Nieuwenhuysen, Belgium
Dr. Azhar Kazmi, Saudi Arabia
Dr. Daniel Chandran, Australia
Dr. Rose Maria Cubilla-Pinilla, Spain

National Advisory board
Prof. S. B. Singh, Ex VC, Lucknow University
Mr. R.S. Tanwar, CEO, SRPL, New Delhi
Sri O. N. Singh, CMD, SGIC, Singapore
Prof. Shailendra Singh, IIM Lucknow
Mr. V. K. Singh, CMD, NCL, Singrauli
Prof. Rajesh Singh, Chairman, PPP Cell, BHU

Editorial Board
Prof. A. K. Agrawal
Prof. Rekha Prasad
Dr. H. P. Mathur
Dr. N. B. Singh
Prof. B. P. Singh, DSE, New Delhi
Prof. Sushil Kumar, IIM, Lucknow
Dr. B. R. Singh, SMC, Mumbai

- Improving Organizational Performance Through
Supply Chain Management Practices by Indian Paint Industry 2-13
**Prof. Deepak Barman, Dr. Ashutosh Mohan
Gyaneshwar Singh Kushwaha**
- System Modeling and Business Performance Evaluation 14-20
D.K. Banwet, K.K. Goswami, Propa Goswami
- Impact of Stress on the Job Satisfaction and Organizational
Commitment of the Sales Force of Pharmaceutical Industry: A Case Study 21-30
Prof. S. K. Singh, Vivek Tiwari, Rajeev Kumar Malik
- Consequences of the Organised Retail
and the FDIs over Retail Sector in India 31-36
Dr. G. C. Jaiswal, Dharen Kumar Pandey
- Factors Affecting Corporate Dividend Policy:
A Case of Nepalese Corporations 37-45
Prof. Raj Kumar, Pawan Kumar Jha
- Role of Television Advertising in Attitude Formation
and Purchase Intention- A Study in Indian Telecom Sector 46-56
Dr. Sathya Swaroop Debasish, Mr. A Mohan Muralidhar
- Sustainable Development Through Marketing:
A Reflection from Retail Industry 57-69
Dr. Ranjana Pandey, Prof. Usha Kiran Rai
- Intangible Value of Corporate India
(Intangible Share in Total Value of Indian Companies) 70-77
Dr. Shital Jhunjhunwala
- Impact of Celebrity Endorsement on Consumers'
Buying Decisions 78-86
Dr. S. K. Dubey, Mr. Pradeep Agarwal
- Competitive Advantage through Human Resources:
A Study in Punjab National Bank 87-96
Saloni Pahuja
- Environmental Accountability: An Urge of Environment to
Bring Some Genuine Changes in Corporate Practices
and People's Lifestyle 97-100
Dr. R.K. Lodhwal, Ms. Kanchan Lata Tripathi

Consequences of the Organised Retail and the FDIs over Retail Sector in India

Dr. G. C. Jaiswal*
Dharen Kumar Pandey**

Abstract

Foreign direct investment refers to the net inflows of investments in any sector in an economy from outside the country from an individual, a group, any financial institution, government, incorporated body or a combination of these. However, there are barriers set by the government about the extent of FDIs in any sector. In this paper, we are focusing towards the growth of FDIs in the retail sector. The pattern of FDI inflows in the Indian retail sector shows a positive effect over the Indian economy. There have been a long discussion over the existence and security of the unorganised retailers and it was found that whatever be the growth of the organised retail sector, the unorganised retailers are going to be and will always be surviving the only thing they should care about is the quality and the rate.

Keywords: FDI, Retailing, Organised Retail, Unorganised Retail.

I. Introduction

Retailing means 'to cut down', i.e. to cut down a huge amount of goods and services into smaller parts which can be of direct use to the direct customer. Retailing owes its origin far in the Vedic age where we would see the small kirana shops by the road side in small towns and villages. Retailing is one of the fastest growing sectors in the world. The Indian retail industry is the fifth largest in the world. Comprising of organized and unorganized sectors, India retail industry is one of the fastest growing industries in India, especially over the last few years. Though initially, the retail industry in India was mostly unorganized, however, with the change of tastes and preferences of the consumers, the industry is getting more popular these days and getting organized as well. Retailing is the most important link between the producer and the individual consumer buying for personal consumption. This excludes direct interface between the manufacturer and institutional buyers such as the government and other bulk customers. A retailer is one who stocks the producer's goods and is involved in the act of selling it to the individual consumer who is the direct utilizer of the product. Thus, retailing is the last link that unites the individual consumer with the manufacturing and distribution chain. The retail industry in India is often being addressed as one of the sunrise sectors in the Indian economy. The AT Kearney, the well-known international management consultancy,

* Professor, Faculty of Commerce, Banaras Hindu University

** Research Scholar, Faculty of Commerce, Banaras Hindu University,

recently identified India as the 'second most attractive retail destination' globally from among thirty emergent markets. It has made India an attraction for the foreign investors. The retail sector contributes 14 per cent to the national GDP and employs over 7 per cent of the total workforce in the country. Thus it is also one of the important pillars of the Indian economy. The attraction of FDIs towards the retail sector has enhanced the growth. II. Objective and Scope of the Study

The paper mainly focuses over the growth of the FDIs in the Indian retail sector. The pattern of FDI inflows and the economic growth has been compared. The growth of the Indian retail sector has also been studied. There is a need to assess the role of FDIs in the growth of Indian retail sector and its effect over the Indian economy. Researchers have also been debating about the security of the unorganised retailers. This paper has also focused upon the security of the unorganised retailers through the thoughts of various eminent authors. This paper will help the readers in enhancing their knowledge regarding the recent pattern of FDIs in the Indian retail sector.

III. Growth of Retail in India

Year	1994-95 to 1999-00	2000-01 to 2002-03	2003-04 to 2006-07	2007-08 to 2010-11
Real GDP	6.6	4.7	8.7	9.1
Retail Sales	13.6	4.8	10.9	11.74

Source: Mathew, J. & Soundararajan, N. (2009). *Retail in India - A Critical Assessment*. Ed by Academic Foundation, N. Delhi. *Current Retail Scene*. Ch. 2. Table 2.3. p35. F & R Research, NSSO, & Macro Economics Report, Ministry of Planning.

India continues to be among the most attractive countries for global retailers. According to the department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP), the Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflows as on September 2009 in single brand retail trading stood at approximately US \$ 47.43 million. Figure 1 below depicts the growth of the retail industry in India during the period 2003-07. The

India has been ranked first for three times in the Global Retail Development Index in a study done by the international consulting firm A. T. Kearney (2005, 2006, and 2007). The Indian retail segment has experienced a positive correlation with the Indian GDP growth. The Indian retail market has been ranked by AT Kearney's eighth annual Global Retail Development Index (GRDI), in 2009, as the most attractive emerging market for investment in the retail sector. Table 1 shows that the gross domestic product (GDP) grew by an annual rate of 6.6 per cent during 1994-00 but the growth slackened to 4.7 per cent per annum during the next three years before the growth remarkably rose to 8.7 per cent per annum during 2003-07. Retail sales (in nominal terms) in the country also followed a similar pattern: a high annual growth of 13.6 per cent during 1994-00, a low growth of 4.8 per cent during 2000-03 and a smart pick up during the period 2003-07 at around 11 per cent (Report by ICRIER, 2009). The report by the ZEE Research Group in 2011 positioned Indian retail at the fourth place in the Global Retail Development Index (GRDI).

Table I

total retail sales have moved up from Rs. 10, 591 billion in 2003-04 to Rs. 14, 574 billion in 2006-07 with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 11.2 per cent. Out of the total retail sales the majority part was shared by the food and grocery section with 66 per cent share in 2003-04, 62.5 per cent in 2004-05, 61.7 per cent in 2005-06, and 59.6 per cent in 2006-07.

Figure : Total Retail Sales Growth in India

(in Rs. Bn.)

Source: ICRIER Report, May 2008 & Indian Retail Report, F & R Research, 2009.

I. FDIs in the Indian Retail Sector

In the year 2006, the government allowed up to 51 per cent FDI in the single brand retail. The FDI inflows have been continuously declining during the period 2009 to 2011. Table 2 shows the FDI inflows during the period January 2010 to May 2011. It is seen that although there has been major downfalls in the FDIs in the retail

sector, the per cent share in the total FDI in the economy was not much varied. This directs us that not only the FDIs in retail sector but in all the sectors have been declining during this period. The negative figures direct us towards the poor performance of the FDIs into the retail sector. The amount of FDIs in the Indian retail sector has been declining.

Table 2: FDI inflows in the Indian Retail Sector

(in Rs Crore)

April 2000 to	FDI in Indian Retail Sector	Percentage to Total FDI in all the Sectors	Total FDI in India	Percentage increase/decrease to prev. yr
Jan-10	8707.97	0.18	4787509	-
Feb-10	8823.97	0.18	4867055	1.66%
Mar-10	901.64	0.18	492203	-89.89%
Apr-10	901.64	0.18	501899.8	1.97%
May-10	907.55	0.18	512035	2.02%
Jun-10	907.55	0.17	518463.7	1.26%
Jul-10	908.27	0.17	526822.5	1.61%
Aug-10	908.27	0.16	533018.6	1.18%
Sep-10	909.77	0.16	542773.1	1.83%
Oct-10	912.37	0.16	548958.2	1.14%
Nov-10	1074.04	0.19	556286	1.33%
Dec-10	1056.39	0.18	565379.5	1.63%
Jan-11	593.41	0.10	570104.7	0.84%
Feb-11	593.41	0.10	575889.4	1.01%
Mar-11	304.85	0.05	580722.4	0.84%
Apr-11	306.12	0.05	594568.8	2.38%
May-11	317.61	0.05	615514.8	3.52%

Source: Compiled from the data available on the Website of the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion.

It can easily be seen in Figure 2 that how the FDI inflows in the Indian retail sector have been declining during the aforesaid period. The inflow of FDIs in retail sector fell from 0.18 per cent in January 2010 to pity 0.05 per cent in May 2011. This shows that in 2011, the FDI inflows were very poor in the retail sector. This may be due to the strict FDI policy prevailing in India.

The trend analysis clearly depicts that the average monthly growth rate in FDIs in retail sector has been -10.62 per cent which means that the performance was really unsatisfactory. The FDIs inflows were more than the trend value during Jan-Feb 2010 and Jan-May 2011 but it was considerably not a realising figure during the year 2011.

Figure 2: Cumulative FDI inflows in the Indian Retail Sector from April 2000 to May 2011

The correlation between the FDIs in the retail sector and the total FDIs in India has been calculated so that their relativeness can be measured. The coefficient of correlation 0.99 shows that they are positively and highly correlated. This positive and higher correlation indicates that the flow of FDI in the retail sector was similarly affected as the total FDI and also that the FDIs in retail sector represents the total FDIs in India. In order to check that the FDIs in retail represented the total FDIs, correlation between these has been calculated for two periods, viz; January 2010 to December 2010 and January 2011 to May 2011. It has been found that the correlation between them during the former period was 0.99 and that for the later was -0.70. It can, thus, be said that the flow of the FDIs in retail sector during the year 2011 has been very poor. Hence, the FDI policy must be liberalised so that the retail sector grows at a free flow.

I. Organised Vs Unorganised Retail Sector

There has been a big discussion over the existence and the security of the unorganised retailers who have always been our neighbours and served us with great diligence. The question was about the sentiments of these retailers who are ready to serve us at any time of the days. We, the modern customers, are moving towards the valuable quality service which the organised retail is providing to us but isn't it the move towards dependency upon Western giants- this is the question by the Gandhian philosophy to Be India, Buy India, Be Happy. Is it that China wants to weaken our economy by its dumping market strategy? Will the growth of organised retail hamper the growth of the unorganised retail? The answers to these questions were very simple. The organised retail sector attracts only a small group of buyers and a large number of buyers are still dependent on the unorganised

retailers. Everyone has the right to get the services which suit to his/her status and this doesn't mean that the unorganised retailers will lose confidence. The organised retail sector is expected to serve on the 20 per cent of the buyers so a large number remains for the unorganised retailers. When we talk about the sentiments of the unorganised and poor retailers it can be said that a policy can never do well to all at the same time; some may instead suffer. When the country has opened the doors for globalisation, there may be some demerits of the same. Policies must support organised retailers but some policies must be such that they safeguard the interest of the unorganised retailers. The restriction of FDIs to just 51 per cent can be referred to as the safeguard for the unorganised retailers. Organised retail is improving the quality of the standard of living of the buyers. The organised retailers are favoured because they add to the general awareness of the consumers which thus enable them in getting quality products at an acceptable rate. Finally, it is concluded that both organised and unorganised retail contributes to the growth of the economy and a balance in both the forms is necessary. There is no lack of security for the unorganised retailers; wherever the buyers may go they will always return back to the unorganised retailers.

II. Conclusion

Indian retail segment is a growing sector and it will continue growing till the organised sector gains its majority and complete market trade is under control of the retail giants. Although the majority of the retail sector in India is in the hands of the unorganised form, the growth of organised retail sector has been impressive. The food & grocery section have been the major contributors in this growth holding approximately about two-third share. Government policies, high cost real estates, unskilled and poor retail knowledge, the tax system and the poor infrastructure facilities are the major problems for a steady growth in the Indian retail sector. It is very necessary for the Indian economy that the retail sector grows because after agriculture, India's strength

completely lies upon the success of trade. Trade has always been an impressive factor in the growth of the economy. The inflow of FDIs in retail sector fell from 0.18 per cent in January 2010 to pity 0.05 per cent in May 2011. It is necessary for the government to free up the regulations for the FDI in Indian retail sector. A liberal policy regarding the FDI investment in retail would also help out this problem. In fact, the regulations for the existence and security of the unorganised retailers must not be neglected.

References

1. Claudia, L. (2005). Technology and applications in the retail supply chain: The early metro group pilot. 18th Bled eConference eIntegration in Action. Bled, Slovenia, June 6-8, 2005.
2. David, L. (2009). Superstores or mom and pops? Technology adoption and productivity differences in retail trade. Research department staff report. 428. Federal Reserve Bank of Minneapolis.
3. FDI Report, FDI Statistic, Department of Industrial Promotion and Policy, Govt. of India
4. Gupta, A. K. (2006). Food retail and branding in India. Retrieved from http://www.on-line-foods.com/tech_paper/Ajay_Gupta.pdf
5. Gupta, P. (2006). Organised retail in India: The next growth frontier. Tata Strategic Management Group Review.
6. Guruswami, M., et al. (2010). FDI in India's Retail Sector, Retrieved from <http://cpasindia.org/reports/10-FDI-Retail-more-bad.pdf>
7. Guruswamy, M.; Sharma, K.; Mohanty, J. P. & Korah, J. T. (2006). FDI in India's retail sector: More bad than good? Retrieved from http://www.indiafdiwatch.org/fileadmin/India_site/10-FDI-Retail-more-bad.pdf
8. India Retail Report 2009 by IMAGES F&R Research. Retrieved from <http://www.indiaretailing.com/india-retail-report-2009-detailed-summary.pdf>
9. Indian Retail Report. F & R Research, 2009. Downloaded from <http://www.indiaretailing.com/india-retail-report-2009-detailed-summary.pdf>
10. Joseph, M., Soundarajan, N., Gupta, M. & Sahu, S. (2008). Impact of organised retailing on the unorganized sector. ICRIER Report.